

Research Article

"G-D's Physics": Earth's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) as the Universe's New "Functional Epicenter"!

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Note: Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in further direct validation of the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics; Dr. Bentovish (Bentwich) e-mail is: drbentovish@gmail.com

Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a basic "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" ("Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) Scientific Paradigm! This Paradigmatic Shift follows a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" found in the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm signified by a basic "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM, and its inability to explain the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion (e.g., assumed to be "caused" by purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe, but which could not be detected despite two decades of trying to do so)?! In contrast, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of resolving this GRT-QM "theoretical-inconsistency" based on the discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe through an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec"! In the current article two "G-D's Physics" unique "Critical Predictions" are being validated empirically – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, thereby "crowning" "G-D's Physics" as the New Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics! Amongst the far-reaching discoveries of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is the identification of Earth's associated "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) as the New "Functional Epicenter" of the Universe, i.e., in "space" and "time", and the postulated "Six-Day Creation" Model which both ensue from the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" CHCF associated "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (CAGUARE) unique "Critical Prediction"!

Introduction

Twenty-first Century Theoretical Physics has reached a state of a fundamental "Paradigmatic-Crisis" – i.e., characterized by the existence of a basic "theoretical-inconsistency" between the two basic "pillars" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm: "General Relativity Theory" (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); and its principle inability to explain the accelerated expansion of the universe, e.g., assumed to be accounted for by purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" concepts, but which failed to be detected empirically even after two full decades of intensive experimental efforts to do so!?

The basic fundamental Paradigmatic Shift brought about by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm is anchored in its basic recognition of the fact that there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame (e.g., since the singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s! Moreover, since according to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, the whole universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the higher-ordered "Universal Computational/

Consciousness Principle" (UCP), there cannot exist any direct or indirect "material-causal" effect, "phenomenon" or interactions/s between any given UF's frame/s and any subsequent UF's frame/s! Therefore, according to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's two profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Principle" theoretical postulates, the physical universe of the universe does not exist as a "constant", "continuous" and "uniform" reality, but is rather seen as a "transient-phenomenal" reality which only exists "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, and is solely computed by the UCP (including the four basic physical features of "space", "energy" mass" and "time" for all exhaustive multifarious spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s), but "dissolves" back into the singularity of this higher-ordered UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, hence termed as "computationally-variant"!?

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics has undergone a major "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" ("Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) [1-47]. This "Paradigmatic-Shift" inevitably followed the appearance of

a fundamental “Paradigmatic-Crisis” of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm signified by a basic “theoretical-inconsistency” between its (above-mentioned) constituting Models (e.g., GRT & QM), as well as its principle inability to explain the accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion, e.g., assumed to be “caused” by purely hypothetical “dark-matter” and “dark-energy” concepts, but could not be detected experimentally (despite over twenty years of intensive experimental efforts to do so)?! Instead, the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) has been shown capable of resolving this (apparent) “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM based on its discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) UCP which simultaneously computes the four basic physical features (e.g., of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”) of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – in the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ (!) thereby producing an extremely rapid series of UF’s frames comprising the entire physical universe at every “minimal time-point”!

According to Thomas Kuhn’s [50], well-accepted analysis of the “Structure of Scientific Revolutions” [50], in order for science to accept such a “Paradigmatic-Shift” (in any given scientific sub-discipline), it is necessary for a few specific conditions to be fulfilled:

a) The appearance of such a “Paradigmatic-Crisis” (in that given discipline) signified by the existence of a “theoretical-inconsistency” between the “pillars” of the Old (“Material-Causal”) Paradigm (e.g., GRT & QM, i.e., as mentioned above), as well as this Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s principle inability to explain the accelerated expansion of the physical universe – e.g., assumed to “caused” by purely hypothetical “dark-matter” and “dark-energy” concepts, which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the matter in the universe but which could not be detected experimentally despite numerous attempts to do so (despite twenty years of intensive experimentation)?!

b) The ability of the New (“G-D’s Physics”) Scientific paradigm to resolve this apparent “theoretical inconsistency” between the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT & QM, as well as offer an alternative (satisfactory) theoretical explanation for the accelerated expansion of the universe: Based on “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm’s discovery of the singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle’s” (UCP’s) simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF’s frame/s), it has been shown that this UCP simultaneously computes all “Single Spatial-Temporal” (SST) “particle/objects”; “Multiple Spatial-Temporal” (MST) “wave-phenomena”; and “Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal” “Universal Frame/s” computations! In this manner, the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of resolving the apparent “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT’s strict “Speed of Light Barrier” (SLB) as opposed to QM’s “Quantum Entanglement” phenomena’s implication wherein a certain measurement of one subatomic “entangled particle’s” (“complimentary pairs” value may “instantaneously” affect the other “entangled particle’s” complimentary (energy/mass or time/mass) value?! This is simply because according to “G-D’s Physics broader EST computation – which embeds (within it) the relatively more “constrictive” UCP’s MST and SST computations, the apparent “Quantum Entanglement” phenomenon merely represents the UCP’s computation of “equivalent SST particle points” along the MST’s (subatomic) “wave” computation, which is embedded within the broader EST UCP’s computation! Alongside “G-D’s Physics” new (profound) theoretical understanding, wherein the UCP’s computation of the four basic physical features of “space” and “energy”, “mass” and “time” is based on the UCP’s two (out of three) “Computational Dimensions” i.e., “Framework” and “Consistency” four possible combinations: “Frame” – “consistent” (“space”) or “inconsistent” (“energy”), and “Object” – “consistent” (“mass”) or “inconsistent” (“time”) possible combinations! Hence, “G-D’s Physics” new theoretical framework has been shown capable of resolving this apparent “theoretical inconsistency” between GRT’s strict SLB’s principle constraint imposed upon the transmission of any signal (or even information) across space and time – which seems to be contra-

dicted by Quantum Entanglement’s “instantaneous” effect of the measurement of one entangled particle’s complimentary pairs’ measurement upon the other entangled particle’s complimentary value; based on the deeper theoretical understanding of “G-D’s Physics” (novel) conceptualization and understanding wherein it is the simultaneous UCP’s computation of “equivalent MST wave” “particle-points”, coupled with its two “Computational Dimensions” complimentary exhaustive UCP’s computation of “Frame” – “consistent” (“space”) or “inconsistent” (“energy”), or “Object” – “consistent” (“mass”) or “inconsistent” (“time”), which can account for the apparent “entanglement” of two such “equivalent SST particle points” along the “MST wave” (simultaneous) computation of the UCP’s “complimentary-exhaustive” “Frame” – “consistent” (“space”) or “inconsistent” (“energy”), or “Object” – “consistent” (“mass”) or “inconsistent” (“time”) “complimentary pairs”!

Likewise, the New “G-D’s Physics” theoretical framework offer a new (satisfactory) alternative theoretical explanation for the universe’s empirically observed accelerated expansion! This new theoretical explanation of “G-D’s Physics” is based on its (novel) “Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis” (CHCFH) which stipulated that whenever there is a large group of individual human-beings all collectively focusing on this singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP), then this brings about an “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE), e.g., such as during the Jewish “Rosh-Hashanah” (New Year) two days’ special time interval (in which Millions of Jews all over the world collectively focus on this singular UCP) – which was predicted to bring about such an “UNCIARE” increase in the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion!

c) Identification of at least one unique “Critical Prediction” which can differentiate the prediction of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT & QM: according to Kuhn’s50 analysis of the “Structure of Scientific Revolutions”, in order for any scientific discipline to accept a basic “Paradigmatic-Shift” from the Old (“Material-Causal”) Paradigm to the New (“G-D’s Physics”) Paradigm it is necessary to identify at least one unique “Critical Prediction” that can differentiate the predictions of the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm from the Old “Material-Causal” GRT’s and QM’s predictions! Indeed, if at least one such (unique) “Critical Prediction” of the New “G-D’s Physics” Paradigm is verified as “more valid” than the corresponding predictions of the Old Paradigm’s GRT’s & QM’s predictions – then (according to Kuhn’s50 well accepted analysis) that particular scientific discipline (e.g., in our case Theoretical Physics) has to accept the New “G-D’s Physics” as the New (satisfactory) Physics Paradigm (for the Twenty-First Century)! Indeed, we’ve been blessed with such an identification of two such (unique) “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm – which are being shown to be “more valid” than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, therefore leading to the unequivocal acceptance of “G-D’s Physics” as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Methods & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New “G-d’s Physics” (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, “G-d’s Physics” identified a unique “Critical-Prediction” stemming from its new “computational definitions” of the four basic physical features of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time” – based on the UCP’s singular higher-ordered two “Computational Dimensions” of “Framework” (frame/object) and “Consistency” (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP’s Computational Dimensions definition of the “mass” of any given particle as an “object-consistent” computational measure:

$$M: \Sigma \{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i...n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the UCP’s computational measure of the “mass” value of any giv-

en object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i...n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by [54-56].

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction

Pohl et al. [54-56], set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} UF(n)] = O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i...n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force"⁴⁹, interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction [53,57], higher dimension gravity [48], a new boson [52], and the quasi-free hypothesis

$\pi+$ [51], and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashana" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion [58-61]. This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Discussion

The key "metamorphosis" brought about by the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm is quite profound: it alters our basic understanding of the physical universe – not as being "caused" or "governed" by any specific "material-causal" physical interactions, e.g., at either the Relativistic or Quantum levels: The universe could not have been "created" or "caused" by any (initial) "Big-Bang" nu-

clear event, because there could not have existed any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels found within the "first", "second"... "nth" "Universal Frame/s" – since they are all being computed simultaneously by the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (or Universal Consciousness Reality", UCR)? Neither, could there exist any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any (two or more) separate UF's frames, simply because all of the exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe – "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP/UCR "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s!? Nor could the "development" or "evolution" of the universe (e.g., once again, at the macroscopic relativistic level or microscopic quantum level) can be explained through any direct or indirect physical interactions between any (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" and any postulated "galactic elements, or indeed, between any subatomic "probe" and "target" elements (which are assumed to "cause" the "collapse" of the target's assumed "probability wave function)!? This is (once again) due to the UCP's/UCR's simultaneous computation of all of the universe's exhaustive spatial pixels' (four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") – for each consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of all of those universe's exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s)!?

In fact, the profound change brought about by "G-D's Physics" New (empirically validated) "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm (for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics) is associated with its discovery of two (far-reaching) theoretical postulates of the "Computational Invariance Principle" and "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR): According to the "Computational Invariance Principle" since only this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) may be regarded as "computationally-invariant", e.g., as existing "uniformly", "continuously" and "constantly" – both "during" its computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s and also exists without the presence of the physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; whereas the whole physical universe (and all of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) is seen (for the first time in Physics) as representing only a "computationally-variant" phenomenon – i.e., existing only "transiently" and "phenomenally" "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely being computed by the UCP), but ceasing to exist and "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" every two consecutive UF's frame/s!? Therefore, only this singular higher-ordered "UCP" may be regarded as "computationally-invariant", e.g., existing "constantly", "continuously" and "uniformly" both "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (and as solely computing all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features comprising the entire physical universe depicted by each such consecutive UF's frame/s), and also solely existing "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence) of any physical universe; whereas the entire physical universe is seen as representing only a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered UCP!? Consequently, the "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulate goes further to highlight the fact that there truly exists only one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" which is this "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) "computationally-invariant" reality – that exists both "during" its computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s, (e.g., manifesting as the entire physical universe), and also exists solely without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

This profound "Paradigmatic-Shift" – i.e., from a purely "Material-Causal" Paradigm assuming that the universe is "caused", "governed" and "developed" by mere (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions (e.g., such as the assumed initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event which is supposed to have "created" the suns, galaxies, planets, energy and mass in the

universe, or the "material-causal" assumption wherein the continuous development of the physical universe is "caused" by the direct interaction/s between certain "massive objects" and "Space-Time" which "curves Space-Time", and conversely this "curved Space-Time" "causes" or "determines" the travelling-pathways of those "massive objects" and other "less-massive objects" etc.); To "G-D's Physics" more extensive understanding of the physical universe as representing a mere ("computationally-variant") "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) completely alters our basic understanding and appreciation of the true "origin", "nature" and higher underlying singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" – i.e., which continuously "computes", "dissolves", "re-computes" and "develops" every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe towards an "Ultimate Geulah Perfected State" of the universe and of Humanity! This is because "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm strictly negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any single or multiple UF's frame/s – due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any such UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such (exhaustive) spatial pixels "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Moreover, based on "G-D's Physics" (abovementioned) two "Computational Invariance Principle" and "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) theoretical postulates, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm completely alters our basic understanding of the "true nature", "origin", "development" and even "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe! This is because not only do we understand that there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (existing either in the "same" or "different") UF's frame/s; but more profoundly, we realize that there only exists one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests as the entire physical universe ("during" each consecutive UF's frame/s), and solely remains "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

So, we realize that the physical universe does not represent any "solid", "independent" "continuous" reality, but rather exists only as a manifestation of the true singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" – which (solely) embodies it and also transcends it! Indeed, the (abovementioned) "A-Causal Computation" characterization of "G-D's Physics" new Scientific Paradigm, which (principally) negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels within the entire physical universe – i.e., existing within any single UF or across any two (different) UF's frame/s; teaches us that the sole "driving force" behind the "origination" - "sustenance" - "development" - and even "Ultimate Goal" of the "formation" and "existence" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe is entirely dependent and contingent upon the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" that constitutes its sole "reality", and which exists "independently" (and "separately") from its "transient-phenomenal" manifestation as the physical universe! Indeed, "G-D's Physics" new realization wherein this singular higher-ordered UCR existence "transcends" it's only "transient-phenomenal" manifestation as the physical universe (e.g., "during" each consecutive UF's frame – as solely being computed by this singular higher-ordered UCR), alongside "G-D's Physics" discovery of this UCR's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's) and associated "THCD's – Universal Computational Formula" (see below Figure and Diagram) reveal to us the real underlying "pre-planned Blueprint Plan" of this UCR to "steer" the entire physical universe – e.g., from its initial "inanimate" matter state through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of the universe (and Humanity), in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this singular higher-ordered UCR, alongside its "sublime" char-

acteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" (which will also affect and characterize Humanity's understanding and behavior)!

A "Pre-Planned Geulah Driven Universe"

We thus reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the universe could not have been "created" or ("caused") by any initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor could its development be explained by any (purely hypothetical and "undetectable") "dark-matter" or "dark-energy"?! but is rather being continuously computed- "dissolved"- "re-computed" and "developed"- by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec)!" thereby producing an incredible rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's), which comprise the entire physical universe at every consecutive "minimal time-point"! Moreover, we realize that not only there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s, but truly all of these exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., including their four associated physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") – do not exist "independently" or "continuously", but rather only represent a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (e.g., which exists "constantly", "uniformly" and "continuously" both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also exists solely without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s)!

Hence, we realize that we cannot (any longer) view the universe's existence as governed by mere "material-causal" physical interaction/s, because such "material-causal" (e.g., direct or indirect) physical interactions cannot "exist" – either between two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels found within the "same" or "different" UF's (due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels of each consecutive UF's frame/s), or "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s, in which the whole universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP!? We therefore must alter our basic understanding of the "origin"- true "nature", "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe – as a mere "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality"! The physical universe exists – not as "independent", "solid", "continuous" reality, but is rather totally dependent upon- and in fact is only a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of- the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which solely exists both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s (exhaustive spatial pixels) and continues to exist without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two (such) consecutive UF's frame/s (in which all of those exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCR!) So, we begin realizing that the entire physical universe – truly only represents a continuous process of "manifestation" and "development" by this singular UCR, which constitutes the only "computational-invariant" "continuous", "uniform" and "constant" reality underlying- and (indeed) "transcending" the entire physical universe!

The next advancement in our understanding of the manner in which this singular UCR reality "originates", "sustains" ("dissolves") and "develops" each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the universe as a whole) is related to the discovery of the UCR's (or UCP's) "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" and associated "THCD's-Universal Computational Formula" (THCD's-UCF)!

Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions

The UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD's)

1)The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה")

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution"- re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!?), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of "All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah " State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality!? Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/"דעת").

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah ' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic , "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral

Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past"- "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blue-Print", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/ דעת) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חסד"/"Chessed"):

This "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/ חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah " may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath

back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("גבורה"/"Devorah"):

Denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" on order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("תפארת"/"Tiferet"):

The sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human -being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th, 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to

bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת"/Tiferet which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification-or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("ניצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

Signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of "ניצח"/"Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva"/("תשובה")/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva" / "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("ניצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("ניצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced

by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "יסוד"/"Yessod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "יסוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude" ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "יסוד"/"Yessod"- "Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computa-

tional Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כֶּתֶר"/"Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "כֶּתֶר"/"Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational

Formula"/"מַלְכוּת"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כֶּתֶר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown"); This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ (sec)" for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

Figure 1: THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS' UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF):

A "Geulah-Driven" Space-Time Evolution of the Universe!

Hence, the alternative theoretical explanation offered by "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- evolution- and indeed the "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe's development is given through "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or UCR), and its associated THCD-UCF! Perhaps another "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor may be helpful, in order to illustrate the (possible) manner according to which this singular (higher-ordered) UCR has "preplanned" the entire origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe: from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – towards the fulfillment of the "Perfected Ultimate Geulah Goal", in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, e.g., including its intrinsic characteristics of "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

According to this "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor, King Solomon had to "preplan" the whole design and build-up of the (immaculate) Temple from its "Completed-Perfected-Final" stage – "backwards" towards the initial stages of its construction, so that this "Blueprint Plan" will lead up to this "Completed-Perfected-Final" state of the Temple! (We could not imagine a scenario in which King Solomon's builders begin "constructing" this Immaculate Temple – without such a "perfected Blueprint Plan", i.e., just by "experimenting" with different stones with no "preplanned Blueprint Plan" for its orderly completion?!) Equivalently, "G-D's Physics" New (Twenty-First Century's) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm postulates that this singular higher-ordered UCR has "preplanned" a "Blueprint Plan" – from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" towards the initial stages of "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, and up to the "Perfected Geulah State" of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCR! Indeed, once we fully realize that there cannot exist any "ma-

terial-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (consecutive or even non-consecutive) UF's frame(s), we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire evolution of the whole universe cannot be "caused" by any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive" objects and their (assumed) "curvature" of "Space-Time" (or the corresponding determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive" or other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by this assumed "curved Space-Time" fabric), as GRT postulated! Instead, we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, the whole universe is being continuously "created", "dissolved", "re-created" and "evolved" so many "trillions" of time each second –by this singular UCR! Moreover, we realize that the sole manner in which the entire physical universe evolves, is based on this preplanned "Blueprint Plan" of advancing the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah-Goal" State! Indeed, we currently stand at a "historic time", e.g., equivalent perhaps to Eddington's empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" of Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion's curvature around the Sun – with the empirical validation of two such (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's Models! Moreover, this empirical validation of those two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – in fact, point at the attainment of Humanity's (and Science's) "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State! This is because the very definition of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe is precisely one in which Humanity recognizes the singular reality of this UCR, i.e., underlying (and transcending) the entire physical universe, and being characterized through its basic intrinsic properties of: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will also characterize ("guide" and "typify") Humanity's newly "Perfected Geulah State"!

FIGURE 2: The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

**The UCP'S "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions –
Universal Computational Formula" (THCD's-UCF):**

We therefore begin realizing that the whole "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the entire physical universe is driven by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe in order to reach that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the universe, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"! We realize that since the UCP is the sole "computationally-invariant" Principle (or "reality") that can "produce"- "sustain"- "dissolve"- or "evolve" any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, as well as "originate"- "sustain" and "evolve" the entirety of the physical universe! And moreover, since that the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is continuously "originating"- "evolving"- ("dissolving"-) and "developing" the entire physical universe – is "motivated" by this singular higher-ordered UCP's/UCR's intrinsic "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony", and geared towards fulfilling the Universe's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal" State of the Universe (and of Humanity)! Therefore, we are "astonished" to find out that at every "trillionth-of -trillionth etc." of a second (e.g., "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec!) this UCP computes and evolves every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – including all human-beings, animals, plants and even "inanimate matter" based upon the UCP's THCD's (and associated THCD's-UCF!) which is "steering" the universe (and Humanity) towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and begin living in accordance with this UCP's/UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

The important point to be noted (here) is that we begin noticing that the manner in which this UCP computes- sustains- ("dissolves"-) and evolves- every exhaustive spatial pixel (as well as the entirety of the whole universe) relies upon its THCD's extremely rapid computation, e.g., at the rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec! in which the "Human Collective Consciousness Focus" (as well as the Individual Human Consciousness Moral Choice/s) plays a key central role, alongside this singular higher-ordered UCP's "steering" of Humanity and the Universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State"! This is because, when we closely examine those THCD's we notice two very important elements:

a) **The sixth Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of the Universe's Expansion (NCARUE) at the Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH) – determines the universe's increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion, i.e., beginning at each JRH's two days' special time-interval!** (This year the UNCIARE-JRH took place during Sep. 16th-17th, 2023, for which there was an urgent Call for Astronomers to validate the increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion beginning in these two days and subsequently, relative to the rate of the universe's expansion prior to these two days' JRH time-interval! Data is still missing regarding this urgent call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to validate this year's Sep. 16-17th UNCIARE.) Nevertheless, one of the two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – which have been empirically validated as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM is this UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction! As shown above, this "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE (JRH) "Critical Prediction" was validated empirically based on the "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (CAGUARE) which supports "G-D's Physics" annual increase at the JRH's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) two days' time-interval! Indeed, such a CAGUARE cannot be accounted for GRT's "constant-rate" expansion of the universe due to the (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" concepts – but precisely confirms "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction"! This is because based on "G-D's Physics" CHCF postulate which takes place every consecutive JRH's (two days' time interval and remains constant throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year) it is expected that the universe's expansion rate will increase "over time", i.e., leading to the observed CAGUARE's UNCIARE-JRH phenomenon!

b) **Earth's CHCF "Functional Center" of the Universe – In "Space" & "Time"!!** Indeed, the existence of "Hubbles Law" (HL), e.g., indicating that the rate of the universe's expansion – relative to "Earth's Functional Epicenter" increases as a function of the distance of any give galaxy from "Earth's Functional Epicenter" points at Earth functioning as the "Universe's Functional Epicenter"! Moreover, when we take into consideration the combination of HL's Earth's Functional Center together with the (abovementioned) CAGUARE UNCIARE-JRH we must reach the inevitable conclusion wherein Earth's CHCF stands at the basis of Earth's Functional Center – i.e., both in "space" and "time"! In other words, the clear empirical evidence positioning Earth as the "Functional Center" of the universe, as evidenced by HL & associated CAGUARE UNCIARE-JRH indicate that

Earth's CHCF is responsible for Earth's UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., every consecutive Jewish Year), and when taken together with HL indicate that Earth's CHCF serves as the "Functional Center" of the entire physical universe both in "space" and "time"!

c) The UCP's "Non-Continuous Computation of the Universe" (UCP-NCCU)!

The next "step" in our new understanding of the fundamental "metamorphosis" that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm creates in our basic understanding of the true "origin", "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe is associated with "G-D's Physics" other unique "Critical Prediction" validation, e.g., associated with the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings! According to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, the UCP's computation of the entire physical universe (as well as of any of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) is "non-continuous", i.e., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, but "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two subsequent UF's frame/s (e.g., therefore the whole physical universe has been redefined as representing only a "computationally-variant" manifestation of the singular "computationally-invariant" UCP which exists "constantly, continuously and uniformly" both "during" its computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely existing without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s!) Indeed, "G-D's Physics" (second) "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings' unique "Critical Prediction" – differentially predicted this "Proton Radius Puzzle" key findings, wherein the relatively "more massive" Muon particle would be computed by the UCP as more "spatially-consistent" than the relatively "less-massive" electron particle (across a series of UF's frame/s)! This is because according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm the UCP's computation of any given particle's "mass" value is based on the UCP's "Object-consistent" computation of each given particle – i.e., with more massive particles being computed as more "spatially-consistent" (as outlined previously) This leads to the UCP's computation of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle as being more "spatially-consistent" than the less-massive electron particle, which then leads to the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings of the relatively "smaller, more accurate measurements" of the Hydrogen's Proton Radius – when encircled by the relatively "more massive" Muon particle, than when encircled by the "standard electron" particle! But, implied within this empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" unique "Proton-Radius Puzzle" "Critical Prediction" is the realization that the UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entire physical universe) – is "non-continuous", i.e., "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, as indicated above, "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in either the "same"- or "different" UF's frame/s, which also implies that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

As shown above, "G-D's Physics" two profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates indicated that the only manner in which the "computationally-variant" universe is "originated", ("dissolved"), "sustained" and "developed" – at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ " is based upon the UCP's THCD's-UCF, which has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards reaching the universe's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah" State of the universe, in which both Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this UCP, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" & "Harmony"!

Since the UCP's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe relates to Humanity's attainment of such a "Perfected Geulah State", in which all human-beings realize their "oneness" with this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, i.e., including their realization of the UCP's basic fundamental "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle": which "teaches" every individual human-being to regard any other human-being as "integral inseparable parts" of this same singular higher-ordered UCP, therefore we see that the UCP's execution of every consecutive UF's exhaustive spatial pixels – strongly relates to its computation of each individual human-being's Moral Choice/s at every "minimal time-point", including the (previously delineated) possibility of "Teshuvah" (e.g., corresponding to the UCP's eighth "Teshuva" HCD, which allows every human-being to carry out a sincere "Teshuvah" remorse and conscious decision to not repeat any specific immoral action); which then alters and changes the UCP's computation of the subsequent (ninth) "UCP's Actual Computed Object", (i.e., in terms of "avoiding" and "altering" that individual human-being's next subsequent UF's frame/s presentation of an "equivalent negative situation" in which that individual human-being would have to experience the same "negative immoral situation" which he/she inflicted pain/suffering upon any other individual human-being – since that individual human-being has carried out a genuine "teshuvah" regarding his/her "immoral choice/s")! So, we can see that at the very center of the UCP's continuous creation- sustenance- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entire physical universe's development) stands the UCP's consideration of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – at the JRH's two-days' time-interval, which brings about the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCI-ARE), as well as the UCP's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle which affects that UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in any subsequent UF's frame/s of the universe), and advances the whole of Humanity towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe!

A "Geulah-Driven" Space-Time Evolution of the Universe!

Hence, the alternative theoretical explanation offered by "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- evolution- and indeed the "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe's development is given through "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or UCR), and its associated THCD-UCF! Perhaps another "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor may be helpful, in order to illustrate the (possible) manner according to which this singular (higher-ordered) UCR has "preplanned" the entire origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe: from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – towards the fulfillment of the "Perfected Ultimate Geulah Goal", in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, e.g., including its intrinsic characteristics of "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

According to this "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor, King Solomon had to "preplan" the whole design and build-up of the (immaculate) Temple from its "Completed-Perfected-Final" stage – "backwards" towards the initial stages of its construction, so that this "Blueprint Plan" will lead up to this "Completed-Perfected-Final" state of the Temple! (We could not imagine a scenario in which King Solomon's builders begin "constructing" this Immaculate Temple – without such a "perfected Blueprint Plan", i.e., just by "experimenting" with different stones with no "preplanned Blueprint Plan" for its orderly completion!?) Equivalently, "G-D's Physics" New (Twenty-First Century's) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm postulates that this singular higher-ordered UCR has "preplanned" a "Blueprint Plan" – from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" towards the initial stages of "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, and up to the "Perfected Geulah State" of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity

of this UCR! Indeed, once we fully realize that there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (consecutive or even non-consecutive UF's frame/s), we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire evolution of the whole universe cannot be "caused" by any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive" objects and their (assumed) "curvature" of "Space-Time" (or the corresponding determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive" or other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by this assumed "curved Space-Time" fabric), as GRT postulated! Instead, we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, the whole universe is being continuously "created," "dissolved," "re-created" and "evolved" so many "trillions" of time each second – by this singular UCR! Moreover, we realize that the sole manner in which the entire physical universe evolves, is based on this preplanned "Blueprint Plan" of advancing the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah-Goal" State! Indeed, we currently stand at a "historic time," e.g., equivalent perhaps to Eddington's empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" of Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion's curvature around the Sun – with the empirical validation of two such (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's Models! Moreover, this empirical validation of those two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – in fact, point at the attainment of Humanity's (and Science's) "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State! This is because the very definition of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe is precisely one in which Humanity recognizes the singular reality of this UCR, i.e., underlying (and transcending) the entire physical universe, and being characterized through its basic intrinsic properties of: "All-Goodness," "Morality," "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will also characterize ("guide" and "typify") Humanity's newly "Perfected Geulah State"!

Intriguingly, based on the discovery of these THCD's characteristics of the operation of this singular higher-ordered UCR (and associated THCD's-UCF), we realize that the whole "origination," "sustenance," and "development" of the entire physical universe has been "preplanned" by this singular higher-ordered UCR in order to advance the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter form through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the Ultimate "Geulah Perfected Goal" state of the universe, in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, and its THCD's ("sublime") characteristics including: "All-Goodness," "Morality," "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will therefore also typify Humanity's Perfected "Geulah Goal" State (behavior and attitude towards each other etc.)! According to this New "G-D's Physics" THCD's Geulah-Goal Directed Universe's theoretical perspective, the universe was not created (or "caused") by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor has its evolution been the result of any ("random": direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – including its (abovementioned) negation of the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts, or "Cosmological Constant" etc.; but rather as originating from the UCP's/UCR's "preplanned Blueprint Plan" to develop the universe from its "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading up to that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity and the universe! In order to perhaps (further) elucidate this novel conception of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, we can utilize the "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" (which has been used previously) to explain this new conception of the universe's development: If we were to imagine a certain "action-film" such as "James Bond's" famous films, we could envision a whole "cascade of events" in which James Bond escapes "grave dangers" in order to protect the "vital interests" of his government (and the whole free world), ultimately leading to the abolishment of the "evil organization" trying to sabotage "world-peace", and fulfillment of

such a desired "World-Peace Agreement" that would advance Humanity towards a "cooperative, peaceful and prosperous future"... But, if we analyze (deeper) this Cinematic-Film Metaphor scenario, we could see that the whole progression and "plot" of the film has been "pre-planned" before the "shooting" of the film! In fact, we could not imagine any "occurrence" taking place within the film which would "affect" or "alter" this "pre-planned plot" of the film, nor any "interactions" occurring within the film! On the contrary, we realize that all of these (apparently) "random occurrences" were "pre-planned" by the producer of the film in order to lead us (the "viewers" of the film) to realize a certain "motto" of this ("thrilling") "James Bond Action Film" – i.e., such as: to believe that there is always a "good-ending" in Life, and that "good prevails"! In much the same manner, it is suggested that this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading up to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity and the universe, and therefore that the whole "origination," "sustenance" and "development" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entirety of the whole physical universe) develops solely based on this singular higher-ordered UCP's/UCR's (preplanned) "Perfected Geulah Goal Directed Universe" Blueprint Plan!

In other words, we must embrace an entirely new conception of the entire "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the physical universe: which was not created by an initial "random Big-Bang" nuclear event, or that is being expanded (at an accelerated rate) by purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts; Instead the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm explains the whole "origination"- "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe (as well as of every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) solely based on the fulfillment of the UCP's/UCR's preplanned "Blueprint Plan" for a "Geulah Perfected Goal Driven Universe"! Therefore, instead of assuming that the universe was created by a random initial ("Big-Bang") nuclear event (which is assumed to have "caused" the creation of all the suns, galaxies, planets, mass and energy in the universe); and moreover (based on this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumed "Darwin's Natural Selection Principle", DNSP – which were all negated by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" empirically validated Scientific Paradigm) that the various Biological forms' evolution on Earth were also created by "random" "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "genetically-mutated" organisms and a "challenging environment" etc.; the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm stipulates that the whole development of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings – all leading to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of Humanity recognizing the singularity of this UCP/UCR and behaving in accordance with this UCP's/UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

Moreover, based on the direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, which is dependent upon the (stipulated) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) (e.g., of Millions of Jews praying and focusing on this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, i.e., in religious terms: "G-D")! therefore, according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm it is clear that the increase in the universe's accelerated expansion rate (e.g., manifesting through the otherwise unexplained abovementioned CAGUARE phenomenon) – is contingent upon the existence of such CHCF (UNCIARE-JRH) every consecutive year, from the very "beginning" of the universe and up till today! In other words, according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm the whole evolution and expansion of the entire physical universe – and specifically the (otherwise unexplained CAGUARE phenomenon) critically depends upon the CHCF associated with the JRH's UNCIARE (e.g., em-

pirically validated by "G-D's Physics" Critical UNCIARE prediction above, and urgent call for Astronomers testing of the specific UNICARE-JRH increase in the universe's expansion accelerated rate during the upcoming JRH on the 16th-17th of Sep., 2023!) This means that according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm's (empirically validated) CHCF, and associated THCD's-UCF (which delineates the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR computes every consecutive UF's frame/s at the unfathomable rate of " $c^2/h = 1/36-50 \text{ sec}!$ "), it is hereby stipulated that the UCP's/UCR's initial "origination" of the whole universe – including its complete "progression" from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings took place in only six (or seven) days (i.e., to include the "Ultimate Geulah Goal State")!

This is because it is only "logical" to assume that if the UCP/UCR simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ (sec!)}"$ by employing specifically those seven HCD's which are computing and "materializing" each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (based on the Three Initial Key HCD's which together comprise the THCD's!); and if indeed (as proven empirically through "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction") the continuous increase in the universe's expansion rate critically depended upon the presence of human-beings and their capacity to carry out this CHCF-JRH for each consecutive years since the UCR's "origination" of the universe (e.g., till the current time); therefore, it is "logical" to assume that the UCR has created the whole universe based on its seven HCD's (e.g., corresponding HCD for each day!)

Plausibility of "G-D's Physics" New "Universe's Seven Days Origination" (USDO) Model

It is important to note (on a philosophical-scientific level) that since the actual capacity of Science (or Physics) to carry out any direct measurement of the "origination" of the universe – is strictly negated by GRT, due to the fact that we cannot move at a speed exceeding the "Speed of Light" (and therefore cannot "move back in time" to directly observe the actual "origination" of the universe!) therefore, we can only "contrast" between different Scientific Paradigms – such as the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying GRT's "Big-Bang" Model) and the New "G-D's Physics", and consequently decide which of these Scientific Paradigms prevails! Significantly, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm has been proven to be "more valid" than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM) based on the empirical validation of its two unique "Critical Predictions" – e.g., associated with the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings and the UNCIARE (JRH)! Hence, the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model was negated based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, and therefore its THCD's-UCF theoretical explanation of the continuous "origination", "dissolution" "sustenance", and "development" of the entire physical universe – towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" must be accepted, including its corresponding stipulation of the "seven days creation" of the entirety of the universe (e.g., with all "inanimate" and "animate" forms including human-beings!) Indeed, a further (even more direct) empirical validation (previously called for Astronomers to carry out) that would test for the appearance of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle in a greater number of "Fine-Temporal Measurements" (FTM) in a greater number of UF's than the equivalent (negatively charged) electron particle would directly validate the ongoing continuous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP, e.g., giving further support for "G-D's Physics" stipulated (novel) "UCP's Severn Day Creation Model" (UCP-SDCM)!

Over and beyond the clear (abovementioned) validation of two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of

the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, which forces Science to accept "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-first Century (valid) Scientific Paradigm, there are several further supporting elements taken from "G-D's Physics" "internal-validity" also pointing at the plausibility of its USDO Model of the origination, as part of the basic "Geulah Perfected State Driven Universe" new understanding of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm!

a) It is clear that the universe could not be caused by the initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor could its accelerated rate of expansion could be accounted for by the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts, nor through Einstein's Equations' three EEE's (as negated by "G-D's Physics" CDP)!

b) Moreover, based on "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm (as noted above) due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, we reached the inevitable conclusion that the universe cannot evolve based on any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s), and therefore that the only "viable means" for explaining the origination- sustenance- "dissolution"- re-computation- and development of the entire physical universe (or of any of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) can only be given based on the analysis of the singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR that is continuously "originating" – "dissolving" "re-creating" and "evolving" every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}!$ ")

c) The complete "dependence" – and in fact "inseparability" of the entire physical universe from this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is significantly strengthened based on the (abovementioned) profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates – which indicates that there exist only this one singular reality, which is this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP) that exists both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, according to these two (profound) theoretical postulates the entire physical universe (and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels) does not exist "independently" of this singular UCR – but rather merely represents a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular UCR reality!

d) Hence, we realize that the whole existence- (continuous) origination- sustenance- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe totally depends upon the "intrinsic characteristics" of this singular UCR/UCP, which were discovered as the UCP's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's), alongside the UCP THCD's Universal Computational Formula: as noted above (and previously), these UCP's THCD's and (associated) UCF – all point at "G-D's Physics" "Geulah Driven Universe"! In other words, these UCP's THCD's point at the UCP's "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" for advancing the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of Humanity and the universe!

e) Indeed, according to "G-D's Physics" "Reversed Time Geulah Goal" postulate, the whole "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR from its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and its "sublime" characteristics (e.g., THCD's) specifically leading to the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected State" of "Peace", "Harmony", "Morali

ty" and "All-Goodness" (which will therefore also characterize Humanity's Geulah State and accompanying behavior!)

f) When taken together with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) "Critical Prediction" increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion stipulated to occur during the two days' Jewish "Rosh Hashanah" (New Year) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – which was empirically supported based on the observed (and otherwise "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" [CAGUARE]); and more specifically, the current call for Astronomers & Cosmologists to empirically validate a more direct "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" regarding the UNCIARE's increased rate of the universe's expansion predicted to take place during the upcoming JRH on Sep. 16th & 17th, 2023 (e.g., relative to prior to Sep 16th-17th, and carry over in an increased universe's accelerated rate of expansion throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year!) These results clearly indicate that the empirically validate CAGUARE (supporting "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction", as explained above and previously) supports "G-D's Physics" centrality of the CHCF as key in explaining the UNCIARE increase in the universe's rate of expansion over the course of the universe's development course (rather than "G-D's Physics" negated purely hypothetical "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" or any of Einstein's other tree EEE's, as described above!)

g) This means that presence of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) must have existed from the initial "origination" of the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR! Specifically, when taken together with the UNCIARE-JRH indication that this empirically validated UNCIARE may take place during the JRH's two days' time interval then this implies that from the "first year" of the universe's "origination" by the UCP/UCR, there must have existed this UNCIARE-JRH's CHCF that allowed the (initial) "accelerated expansion rate of the universe! This implies that from the universe's "origination point" by the UCP, shortly after its initial origination, there must have occurred this CHCF JRH UNCIARE phenomenon!

h) When taken together with "G-D's Physics" THCD's UCF (precise) description of the manner in which the UCP accurately computes each subsequent UF's (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec") based primarily upon the UCP's (consecutive) computation of the "seven secondary HCD's" (as "preplanned" and "executed" by the UCP's Three Key Initial HCD's Blueprint Plan for steering the universe from its inanimate through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State") – then this suggests as "plausible" and "reasonable" that the UCP's initial "origination" of the entire physical universe – from its initial "inanimate" state through its pre-planned subsequent "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (and even perhaps initial recognition by a human-being of the singularity of this UCP, i.e., "G-D" Presence) may have occurred during the first seven days – one day for each of these secondary seven HCD's! Subsequently, after this "first week" in which all "animate" and "animate" (plants, animals and human-beings) have been "originated" by the UCP/UCR, it is suggested that the first CHCF JRH-UNCIARE occurred which allowed for the UCP's first UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!

Hence, it's become clear that Science (and Humanity) have now reached a "critical turning point" in its development: instead of Science's "lifelong" basic "Material-Causal" assumption (e.g., including even "Newtonian Classical Mechanics") wherein it was assumed that everything in the universe can be explained as being "caused" by a certain "material-causal" (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any given (finite) number of material elements!? Such as GRT's basic assumption, wherein the origination of the entire physical universe was "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang"

nuclear event, or the expansion of the universe is "caused" by the purely hypothetical "Dark Matter" or "Dark-Energy" concepts? Or such as QM's assumed determination of any given subatomic particle or wave entity based on the direct physical interaction/s of a given subatomic "probe" element with a corresponding subatomic "target's probability wave-function", which "causes" this (assumed) "target's probability wave function" to "collapse" into a single "complimentary" "space-energy" or "mass-time" value?! The New empirically validated "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm completely negated such basic "Material-Causal" assumption – e.g., due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Therefore, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm advanced our new (higher) understanding wherein the only manner in which this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) continuously "originates", "sustains", ("dissolves") and "develops" the entire physical universe is based upon its "pre-planned" Blueprint Plan of "steering" the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of the entire physical universe in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP as the sole reality behind the universe (e.g., and also transcending its existence); which will also include Humanity's recognition of this singular higher-ordered UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" & "Harmony" which will therefore also characterize Humanity's "peaceful", "meaningful" and "harmonious" ("goodwill") existence!

Dedication

This article is dedicated to the Great Lubavitcher Rabbi whose "Geulah" Teaching to the World is making a profound change in Humanity's seeking to attain such a "Perfected Geulah State" (which is very much needs in the current global situation) – may the discovery of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century assist Science and Humanity get closer to attaining this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of Humanity and the Universe!

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